

Imaginary Average Momentum and Resolution in Quantum Bound States

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In classical mechanics, observables are usually represented by real numbers, not imaginary ones. In quantum mechanics, however, it is possible to have imaginary average values at x , in particular, for average momentum in a bound state. We argue that the observable energy is real and is associated with each x point for a time-independent bound state. Thus, there is an overall momentum of $P=0$ for the whole system because it is not moving in space. Nevertheless, there is a spatial resolution in a bound state (which partly explains why bound states are mathematically orthogonal). Spatial resolution is linked with momentum, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$, and the spatial resolution appears because one uses: $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Thus, average p at each x cannot be 0 and even though it is imaginary, we suggest that it has physical meaning, linked to the spatial resolution.

We further argue that this notion of spatial resolution carries over to the potential $V(x)=\text{Sumover } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$, so the statement that one has a sharp well boundary at $x=a$ is an average one. In reality, momentum hits from the potential are linked with $\exp(ikx)$ terms which also have a resolution. Thus, one cannot say that a square well potential exists at $x=-L/2$ and $x=L/2$, it only does so on average. Thus, there is really no issue with having the wavefunction extend beyond $-L/2$ and $L/2$. On average, however, $KE_{\text{ave}}(x)+V(x)=E_n$ within the classical turning points, for any energy level of a quantum problem. Outside the classical well, one expects a drop-off in $W(x)$. Given that $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$, we argue that one must consider the entire x axis for orthogonality of $W_n(x)$ and $W_{n1}(x)$ because the particle is not physically restricted to $-L/2, L/2$ due to both the spatial resolution of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(ikx)$. Even though one uses an average energy equation (time-independent Schrodinger equation), it is the d/dx d/dx form linked with $\exp(ipx)$ and its spatial resolution which is ultimately responsible for the eigenvalue differential equation which has orthogonal solutions.

Momentum and Spatial Resolution

We have argued in previous notes that a probability which ensures conservation of momentum is $\exp(ipx)$ through orthogonality in x , i.e. $\int dx \exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)=0$ if $p_1 \neq p_2$ in one dimension. This probability, however, introduces a spatial resolution, \hbar/p , which means that even though p and $pp/2m$ (or relativistic E) are precisely known, position is not if one wishes to have conservation of momentum appear mathematically and not be imposed by hand as in Newtonian mechanics.

Given that a particle with momentum p has a resolution \hbar/p , what does it mean to say that a square well potential has a sharp edge at say $-L/2$ and $L/2$? The particle receives a momentum hit k from the potential and this should be associated with $\exp(ikx)$ which has a spatial resolution of \hbar/k . Thus:

$$V(x)=\text{Sumover } k \ V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((1))$$

The edges $-L/2$ and $L/2$ are classical, but do not apply if one has different $\exp(ikx)$ hits. Thus, a quantum particle moving outside the classical turning points is a consequence of different $\exp(ikx)$ spatial resolutions. If a particle is bound in a well, however, one would expect probability $W^*(x)W(x)$ to drop outside the classical boundary conditions. If the particle is not localized in space it is not bound.

We note that within the classical turning points:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

((2)) holds for the classical equation as well as for all energy levels of the quantum. (It also holds outside the turning points, but one has drop off of $W(x)$ and things do not look classical on average there.)

Here:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W \quad ((3))$$

The nature of $\exp(ipx)$ and its spatial resolutions is apparent and $KE_{ave}(x)$ only appears as an average. This suggests that there should be spatial resolution in a bound state with $V(x)$ and in fact there is if one considers a particle in a square well, infinite potential or oscillator etc. This spatial resolution is partially responsible for orthogonality, but this orthogonality must be considered overall x because the particle is not limited to classical turning points.

In solving a square well-potential, one uses the average $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ together with the average $V(x)$. One imposes continuity of $W(x)$ and dW/dx at $-L/2$ and $L/2$ even though this continuity is of an average object $W(x)$. The idea seems to be that $V(x)$ really is a square well between $-L/2$ and $L/2$ on average and in the high energy limit, where resolution is very tiny in space, one has no issue of the particle moving outside the edge (classical turning point), although there is still a tiny tunneling effect.

The Case of Imaginary Momentum Density

In classical mechanics, observables are usually real. In the case of a quantum bound state, energy E is real as is overall momentum $P=0$ if the overall system is not moving. A quantum bound state, however, has internal spatial resolution. In the case of an infinite well potential, this resolution is responsible for orthogonality of wavefunctions $W_n(x)$. This resolution is ultimately connected with $\exp(ipx)$ s and momentum conservation in collisions and so there should be an average p at each x , but this average p , or p density, cannot be real, otherwise it would imply that the whole system were moving. Thus, one has an imaginary p ave or p ave density, but this does not mean that this imaginary value is not physical. We argue that the spatial resolution associated with $p_{ave} = -i dW/dx / W$ or p_{ave} density $-i W dW/dx$ is real and important for orthogonality of W_n due to different energy values. This is built-in to the theory and does not need to be imposed by hand.